

1. BAS - Onboarding Questionnaire

For each section you will be asked if you have one of the sources of usage data - which will guide the information you are asked for. The data sources currently possible for ingesting into BAS are:

- ONIX 3.0 (from ONIX feeds, OAPEN Library, or Thoth Open Metadata)
- JSTOR
- Google Books
- IRUS OAPEN
- IRUS Fulcrum

For any other data sources, or any other questions, please contact the BAS technical team: info@book-analytics.org

* Required

Question 1: Email *

2. ONIX data

Having a valid [ONIX 3.0](#) feed is a requirement for including your book usage data in BAS. We are also able to extract books metadata in ONIX format from the [OAPEN Library](#) and [Thoth Open Metadata](#). If you do not have a suitable ONIX feed, or a book collection hosted on the [OAPEN Library](#) or books metadata hosted on [Thoth Open Metadata](#), please contact us at info@book-analytics.org.

Question 2A: How is your books metadata configured? *

Check multiple if needed.

- Through an ONIX supplier (e.g. ONIXsuite, Booksonix, Coresource, Consonance)
- A collection hosted on the OAPEN Library, accessed via OAPEN's MEMO export module.
- Hosted on Thoth Open Metadata
- Other

Question 2B: What titles will you be sending us in your ONIX feed? *

We do not filter the ONIX data you provide. If you wish your dashboard to only show Open Access titles then the ONIX feed should contain only OA titles. If your ONIX feed contains both OA and closed/paid titles then both will be displayed on the dashboard together.

Mark only one option.

- Only Open Access titles (will be called "Published Open Access Titles" on the dashboard)
- Both Open Access and Closed/Paid titles (will be called "Published Titles" on the dashboard)

Question 2C: Is there anything else about your ONIX feed that you would like us to know?

3. JSTOR usage data

Question 3A: JSTOR *

Do you have [JSTOR](#) usage data that you wish to be included in BAS? *

Mark only one option.

- Yes, we have JSTOR data and wish it to be included in BAS
- Yes, we have JSTOR data but do NOT wish to include it in BAS
- No, we do not have JSTOR data

Question 3B

Field mapping for JSTOR usage data. By default, the BAS dashboard maps downloads to the JSTOR field 'Total_Item_Requests', which is the total number of requests for that book from a specific country or institution. If you wish to have this field mapped differently, please indicate it here otherwise the default will be used.

Question 3C

If there is anything else you would like to add about your JSTOR usage data, please type it here.

4. Google Books usage data

Question 4A: Google Books

Do you have [Google Books](#) usage data that you wish to be included in BAS? *

Mark only one option.

- Yes, we have Google Books data and wish it to be included in BAS
- Yes, we have Google Books data but do NOT wish to include it in BAS
- No, we do not have Google Books data

Tell us more about your Google Books usage data

Question 4B:

How are your books records added to Google Books?

The platform provides two ways to add records that have print and digital versions, as explained in the [ISBNs - Google Play Books Partner Center Help](#)

Mark only one option.

- As a single entry with a primary ISBN and related ISBNs
- Two entries for the print and electronic editions

Question 4C

By default the BAS dashboard maps downloads to the Google Books field '**google_books_sales.Qty**', which is the number of units in the transaction, negative for refunds.

If you wish to have this field mapped differently, please indicate it here otherwise the default will be used.

Question 4D

By default the BAS dashboards maps views to the Google Books field

'**google_books_traffic.BV_with_Pages_Viewed**', which is the number of Book Visits in which users accessed preview pages of a book. This doesn't include visits where a user accessed only informational pages for a book. If you wish to have this field mapped differently, please indicate it here otherwise the default will be used.

Question 4E

If there is anything else you would like to add about your Google Books usage data, please type it here

5. IRUS OAPEN usage data

BAS can collect usage data from books hosted on OAPEN Library through [IRUS usage reports](#) without any other technical information required from you.

Question 5A: OAPEN

Do you have books hosted on OAPEN Library with usage data that you wish to be included in BAS? *

Mark only one option.

- Yes, we have books hosted on the OAPEN platform and wish it to be included in BAS
- Yes, we have books hosted on the OAPEN platform but do NOT wish to include it in BAS
- No, we do not have OAPEN IRUS-UK data

Tell us more about your IRUS OAPEN usage data

Question 5B

By default the BAS dashboard maps **downloads** prior to April 2020 to the IRUS OAPEN field '**title_requests**', which is the total number of title requests. From April 2020 onwards, **downloads** are mapped to the IRUS OAPEN field '**total_item_requests**', which is the total number of item requests.

If you wish to have this field mapped differently, please indicate it here otherwise the default will be used.

Question 5C

If there is anything else you would like to add about your IRUS OAPEN usage data, please type it here

6. IRUS Fulcrum usage data

BAS can collect usage data from books hosted on the Fulcrum platform through [IRUS usage reports](#) without any other technical information required from you.

Question 6A: Fulcrum

Do you have books hosted on the Fulcrum platform with usage data that you wish to be included in BAS?

*

Mark only one option.

- Yes, we have books hosted on the Fulcrum platform and wish it to be included in BAS
- Yes, we have books hosted on the OAPEN platform but do NOT wish to include it in BAS
- No, we do not have OAPEN IRUS-UK data

Tell us more about your IRUS Fulcrum usage data

Question 6B

By default the BAS dashboards map **downloads** to the IRUS Fulcrum field '**total_item_requests**', which is the total number of item requests. If you wish to have this field mapped differently, please indicate it here otherwise the default will be used.

Question 6C

If there is anything else you would like to add about your IRUS Fulcrum usage data, please type it here

7. Miscellaneous questions

Question 7A: Subject schema *

Which subject schema do you wish to use? The default subject schema is BISAC.

Mark only one option.

- BISAC [DEFAULT]
- Thema

Question 7B: Private/Public dashboards

By default all BAS usage dashboards are private (i.e. access-controlled), but there is the option of also having a publicly available dashboard(s). Please select the option that you wish to have.

Mark only one option.

- Private only [DEFAULT]
- Public only
- Private AND public

Question 7C: Data download and dashboard Printing *

There is the option for dashboard users to download data from the charts, and to print or export the dashboard as a PDF. Either both options are available by default, or both options are switched off - it is not possible to have only one or the other enabled.

Mark only one option.

- Allow users to download data from the charts, and to print or export the dashboard as a PDF [DEFAULT]
- No, users can not download data or print or export the dashboard as a PDF

Question 7D: Embedding the dashboard on a website. *

It is possible to have a BAS dashboard embedded within a webpage. If you wish to do this we can provide details required to embed the dashboard.

Mark only one option.

- No, we do not wish to embed the dashboard on a webpage [DEFAULT]
- Yes, we would like to embed the dashboard on a webpage.

Question 7E: Data Start Date *

By default the data in the BAS dashboards will go back to the earliest start date possible, but as there may have been schema changes it is possible that we can't import all of the early data. If you instead wish the start data to be from a particular year, please specify this below, otherwise the default data start date will be used.

Question 7F: Branding *

Do you have a preferred colour scheme? If so, please specify below. The default is that we will select colours from your logo (if provided) or use the default BAS colour scheme.

Question 7G: Naming *

Please indicate your preferred full name for your press/institution so that we can use this in the dashboard.

Question 7H: URL abbreviation

Please indicate your preferred abbreviation for your press/institution so that we can use this in the dashboard URL *

For example

- xyz-press becomes xyz-press.book-analytics.org
- xyzpress becomes xyzpress.book-analytics.org
- xyz becomes xyz.book-analytics.org

Question 7I: Any other information

If there is any other information that you think would be helpful for us to know for onboarding your book usage data into BAS, please type it here.